

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

HYBRID RICE

Retardation of heading in male sterile and restorer lines using paclobutrazol

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Flowering synchronization in parent plants is a key problem in increasing

hybrid rice seed yields. Heading can be promoted by GA₃ treatment, but no one has reported delay in heading by growth regulators.

We sprayed an aqueous solution of 75 ppm paclobutrazol at 11 ml/m² on rice plants at the pollen mother cell formation stage of a cytoplasmic male sterile line (Zhen Shan 97A) and a

restorer line (IR64) growing in the field. Endogenous GA₃ content was determined by leaf sheath bioassay.

Paclobutrazol treatment reduced endogenous GA₃ content in panicles (paclobutrazol is an anti-gibberellin). After treatment, elongating rate of the topmost internode decreased. Beginning of heading was delayed 2-4 d with 1 treatment and 4-6 d with a second treatment 5 d after the first treatment (Table 1).

Foliar spray of GA₃ solution counteracted the retardative effect of paclobutrazol and the plants recovered their height or were even taller (Table 2). The pollen in treated plants developed normally, so did the seeds of the treated and the next generation.

Using paclobutrazol spray at panicle differentiation could adjust synchronization of flowering in male sterile lines and pollen parents and should be conducive to higher crossed seed set. □

Table 1. Effect of 75 ppm paclobutrazol solution on the heading of cytoplasmic male sterile line and restorer line of rice, Guangzhou, China, 1985-86.

Line	Sowing date	Treatment date	Beginning of heading ^a	
			Control	Treated
Restorer line				
IR64	11 Mar 1985	4 Jun	14 Jun	16 Jun
IR64	3 Jul 1986	30 Aug	8 Sep	10 Sep
Cytoplasmic male sterile line				
Zhen Shan 97A	12 Apr 1985	2 Jun	12 Jun	15 Jun
Zhen Shan 97A	17 Jul 1986	4 Sep	14 Sep	18 Sep
Zhen Shan 97A	7 Apr 1986	29 May ^b	9 Jun	12 Jun
Zhen Shan 97A	7 Apr 1986	29 May ^c	9 Jun	15 Jun
		3 Jun ^d		

^a 10% of the panicles have exerted. ^b First treatment, no second treatment. ^c First treatment. ^d Second treatment.

Table 2. Effect of paclobutrazol (Pac) and GA₃ on internode length^a of mature rice plant Zhen Shan 97A, Guangzhou, China, 1986.

Treatment	Topmost internode	2d internode		3d internode		4th internode		1-4 internodes			
		Length (cm)	%	Length (cm)	%	Length (cm)	%	Length (cm)	%		
0	0	20.0 b	100	13.0 b	100	7.1 b	100	3.4 b	100	43.4 b	100
75 ppm Pac	0	16.6 c	83	12.9 c	84	6.6 b	93	3.4 b	100	37.5 c	83
75 ppm Pac	75 ppm Pac	10.2 d	51	6.5 d	50	6.0 b	84	2.8 b	83	25.8 d	59
75 ppm Pac	30 ppm GA ₃	20.2 b	101	13.3 b	102	6.9 b	97	3.0 b	90	43.4 b	100
75 ppm Pac	50 ppm GA ₃	22.5 a	112	23.1 a	178	25.2 a	354	11.3 a	337	82.1 a	189

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test. ^b Conducted at pollen mother cell formation stage.

Evaluation and use of male sterile systems in Mekong Delta, Vietnam

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We evaluated in 1983-86 10 male sterile (A) lines and their corresponding maintainer (B) lines introduced from

China and IRRI.

A and B lines were transplanted in a row ratio of 2:4. Sowing times were adjusted to synchronize flowering. Seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing and received 70-40-30 kg NPK/ha. Rope pulling was used to supplement cross pollination but flag leaves were not clipped and GA₃ was not applied.

Agronomic traits and disease and insect reactions were recorded. Percentage spikelet sterility was determined by bagging five panicles from three plants of each A line at heading in the greenhouse. To estimate outcrossing pollination rate, 20 plants were harvested.

V20A, V41A, Zhen Shan 97A, and Yar ai zhao A did not perform well in

Characters of male sterile lines evaluated in 1983-86 at CLRRI, Omon, Hau Giang, Vietnam.

Male sterile (A)	Maintainer (B)	Maturity (d)	Height (cm)	Tillers (no.)	Panicle exertion	Spikelet sterility (%)	Seed setting (%)		Disease reaction ^a			
							Wet season	Dry season	Wet season		Dry season	
									BB	ShB	ShR	BI ^b
V20A	V20	89	75	10	Fair	100	2	21	5	7	5	2
V41A	V41	95	80	9	Poor	100	6	18	3	7	5	3
Zhen Shan 97A	Zhen Shan 97	93	78	9	Poor	100	2	26	5	7	3	5
Yar ai zhao A	Yar ai zhao	97	77	8	Poor	95	9	27	5	7	5	5
MS519A	IR24	120	95	12	Fair	85	9	17	3	5	3	4
IR46829A	IR19792-15-2-2	95	75	14	Fair	97	9	13	5	7	5	3
IR46830A	IR19807-21-2-2	102	76	16	Fair	100	7	30	5	5	5	-
IR46831A	Jikkoku Surranai 52-37	110	85	18	Fair	92	8	20	3	5	3	6
IR48483A	MS365	110	80	18	Fair	100	6	28	3	5	3	8
IR21845-90-3A (IR54752A)	IR21845-90-3 (IR54752B)	140	110	12	Fair	95	10	19	5	5	3	-
	CV (%)		12.6	15.7								
	LSD (0.05)		14	3								

^a Field evaluation. ^b Evaluated in 1986 blast nursery according to IRRI Standard evaluation system for rice scale.

terms of plant type and reactions to diseases, especially to sheath blight (ShB) (see table). But they showed higher spikelet sterility.

IRRI improved lines IR46830A, IR48483A, and IR21845-90-3A (IR54752A) had acceptable phenotype

with heavy tillering. They were resistant to blast (BI) but moderately susceptible to bacterial blight (BB) and sheath rot (ShR) in the field.

Seed setting in A lines was lower in the wet season than in the dry season.

In general, IRRI improved A lines

showed better adaptability to local conditions than the A lines from China. However, V20A, IR46830A, IR48483A, and IR54752A grew reasonably well and could be used to develop rice hybrids in Vietnam. □

Susceptibility of A lines and B lines to bacterial blight (BB)

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Fifteen isolates of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* were used to

inoculate male sterile (A) lines V20A and Zhen Shan 97A, and their corresponding maintainer (B) lines during the first growing season of 1985. The test was in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Plants were inoculated at booting with a bacterial suspension of about 10⁹

cells/ml, using the clipping technique. Length of lesion was measured 3 wk after inoculation on a sample of 20 leaves/plot.

Cytoplasm affected the expression of BB reaction significantly and interaction between nucleus and cytoplasm was detected (see table). A lines were less susceptible than the B lines. □

Susceptibility of A and B lines to BB. ^a Fuzhou, China, 1985.

Isolate group	Isolate no.	Lesion length (cm)					
		Zhen Shan 97			V20		
		A	B	A-B ^a	A	B	A-B
III	83476-2	26.9	29.4	-2.5*	26.5	28.8	-2.3*
IV	79113-4	27.1	28.5	-1.4	25.8	26.1	-0.9
III	83500-1	26.0	28.2	-2.2**	28.7	27.8	1.0
IV	83505-1	25.6	28.1	-2.5*	26.6	27.3	-0.7
III	82409-3	25.1	27.0	-1.9**	21.2	24.0	-2.8*
III	83498-1	23.1	26.8	-3.7*	22.9	25.0	-2.1**
IV	82443-1	22.8	26.2	-3.4*	24.6	25.1	-0.5
III	82400-1	23.5	27.3	-3.8*	21.6	23.1	-1.5
IV	80153-1	25.3	26.5	-1.2	23.1	22.9	0.2
III	83470-2	23.0	24.4	-1.4	20.8	21.7	-0.9
II	81267-1	23.5	27.1	-3.6*	21.0	22.9	-1.9**
III	83485-3	23.4	23.4	0.0	23.8	22.6	1.2
III	79048-1	21.5	24.7	-3.2*	16.1	17.9	-1.8**
I	81259-7	9.0	9.7	-0.7	9.9	10.7	-0.8
I	81317-3	7.3	8.1	-0.8	7.5	7.6	-0.1

^a Significance at the 1% (**) and 5% (*) levels.

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